

Development of a BIM library for NbS design

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Abstract. The BIM methodology has become a key tool in the civil engineering and construction industry. Through its application to urban development, it can contribute to the design of more resilient cities by incorporating sustainability indicators related to climate data and natural disasters, as well as by creating adaptive designs and generating scenario simulations. Due to the fact that BIM methodology is centered on a 3D model, one of the first steps is to undertake its creation. Despite the fact that there are numerous authoring software for this task, the time required may be high when developing projects related to sustainability-oriented urban development, which can include very specific elements such as Nature-based Solutions (NbS). In order to speed up this process, this paper presents a proposal for a semi-automated library of NbS. This proposal uses a combination of a calculation tool for the automatic dimensioning of the techniques for a specific intervention point, along with a design authoring software to automatically generate BIM objects together with the associated information of the corresponding technique. This work streamlines the process of generating BIM models in urban design.

Keywords: Building Information Modelling, BIM, Nature-based Solutions, NbS

1 Introduction

The use of Building Information Modeling (BIM) throughout the lifecycle of construction projects has evolved rapidly in recent years. Although their numerous benefits are well known, there are still few examples applied to improve urban design aimed at resilience, such as climate adaptation, responses to urban heat island, and sustainable stormwater management. Nevertheless, BIM tools can help to create and visualize different designs and proposals, provide accurate information on built assets, include lifecycle assessment information data, share infrastructure information, estimate connected costs and allow analysis and simulations for future scenarios [1].

Several techniques can be applied to help cities thrive sustainably. One such strategy is Nature-based Solutions (NbS), which can play a relevant role in enhancing urban resilience. NbS helps to mitigate the most common hazards and problems related to urban development. These systems mimic processes that use the natural environment to mitigate these problems and provide additional ecosystem services in urban areas. Their implementation is considered key in achieving European Union policies, such as

the EU Adaptation strategy, aimed to climate change adaptation [2]. Examples include techniques such as permeable pavements, infiltration trenches, green roofs, artificial wetlands or grassed swales.

Incorporating NbS into BIM-based urban projects may contribute to the implementation of sustainable strategies in cities. As BIM methodology centralizes information around a 3D model, one of the steps that should be undertaken is the creation of all the specific 3D objects that compose it, which is a time-consuming task. Even though there is a wide set of BIM authoring software, such specific objects are rarely included in built-in libraries. Moreover, their geometry characteristics and properties depend on a variety of parameters that are different for every project, making it difficult to reuse or adapt them to other works. To facilitate such a task, this communication presents a preliminary proposal for a semi-automated object library of NbS techniques.

The document is organized as follows. After this brief introduction, research on existing solutions is presented in Section 2. Section 3 shows the NbS library as well as the software plug-in developed for automating the final sizing. Then, section 4 resume the overall results, and conclusions are exposed in section 5.

2 Literature review

BIM methodology can be integrated into projects focused on resilience to support a wide variety of tasks with its core in the 3D model of the project. BIM can help to facilitate coordination between stakeholders in preliminary stages, as shown by del Duca et al. [3] who created a 3D risk-map using Revit software for analyzing flood events. In this case, the specific developed objects were limited to topo objects and water bodies obtained from point cloud data for this specific project. Maqsoom et al. [4] used a combination of different software platforms to design a residential scenario that included techniques for rainwater harvesting in buildings using BIM capabilities to calculate the potential storage capacity of rainwater. The 3D objects for the treatment of rainwater were modelled, but without presenting parametric behavior, and only valid for this specific project. Yang et al. [5] developed a tool that combined BIM, GIS, and computational engines to identify vulnerabilities in infrastructure systems in urban flooding situations. In this case, BIM models are aimed to store hazard-sensitive properties of building elements using built-in families, so no specific models were created. Another example is exposed by Huang et al. [6], that research about how BIM modelling can help to detect pipeline surface defects to improve the facility management. Revit is used to generate pipes' models and associate them with inspection information. BIM methodology is also applied by Lanceta et al. [7], that propose a scenario formed by different types of catchments and Sustainable Drainage Systems (SuDS) to simulate hypotheses under different rainfall conditions.

Ock et al. [8] studied the hydrological behavior of a construction site in its design phase using different BIM tools. A 3D model of a detention pond was modeled by a combination of Revit and Civil 3D, and its behavior was analyzed under different scenarios to find its optimal location under different restrictions (slope, pollutant concentration, size, or capacity). Nevertheless, its geometry and dimensions are static;

therefore, its capacity does not change, limiting the restrictions on the stored information. Salvalai et al. [9] combines green roof design with BIM methodology, modeling different case studies with Revit and adjusting material properties to show changes under saturated and dry conditions. This task is carried out throughout Dynamo scripts, analyzing the thermal resistance and weight to evaluate the efficiency and structural feasibility. In this case, although a performance analysis was implemented, the geometry of the roof was manually modified. Stangl et al. [10] propose BIM modelling over green-blue infrastructures by integrating parameters and values with the objective of creating a product portfolio for urban planning, but it is limited to its conceptual design. Finally, Lee et al. [11] developed a BIM library by considering environmental parameters. In this case, built-in objects such as walls, beams, or windows are extended, including properties that allow the calculation of environmental performance as well as economic evaluation at the building design stage.

As a last step, different online BIM libraries have been queried trying to find NbS objects, as UK NBS Source¹ or BIMObject², finding different floor and roofing designs simulating some NbS structures as green roofs or permeable pavement types, which serve as the basis for user modeling, but those found represent specific objects or solutions with inadequate level of development and undesired simplifications.

3 The NBS BIM Library

3.1 Background.

The NbS BIM Library was developed as part of a new methodology designed to enhance hybrid urban drainage solutions, combining grey and green techniques like the NbS. To begin this process, a complete categorized catalogue of NbS was defined, describing their primary uses, applications, possible locations, scale, benefits, and design considerations.

Together with this catalogue, a design spreadsheet was proposed as the computing core for sizing the different NbS for stormwater management based on specific conditions of the site. As this tool was designed as a *blackbox*, the user was required to incorporate the main characteristics of the location and specify the parameters for the desired NbS (such as soil infiltration rate or desired impervious percentage) to numerically calculate the appropriate intervention size for a variety of 13 different techniques. Fig. 1 shows a sample of a linear drainage system factsheet and the calculation results.

The full description of these tool is beyond the scope of this communication but serves as a starting point for the library presented in this document and leads the way for BIM library creation.

¹ <https://source.thenbs.com/>

² <https://www.bimobject.com/>

Fig. 1. (a) Excerpt of a linear drainage system factsheet. (b) Excerpt of the calculation spreadsheet (input data and results) for a grassed swale.

3.2 3D starting objects development.

Considering that the final aim was to automate the creation of the different BIM objects from the spreadsheet calculations, it was necessary to propose a set of starting families, each one of them with different geometric structure, constraints, materials, and parameters. Revit was chosen as the authoring software because of its parametric modelling capabilities, embedded parameter design, interoperability and inclusion of development API. A set of initial restrictions had to be considered: (i) each object had to include a specific layer structure, each one with an associated material, as well as a variable set of property sets related with different parameters (as physical properties, hydrological requirements, costs, or environmental performance) depending on the desired technique; (ii) The different techniques could be presented as linear structures (such as a filter strip) or as elements covering a certain area (such as a detention pond), including also a side slope factor; (iii) some techniques could include additional elements such as pipes or drainage elements in specific layers.

Fig. 2a (3D view) and 2b (elevation view with geometric constraints) show an example of a grassed swale basic family to illustrate this step as well as the level of development of the objects. A swale is a multilayered ditch that collect, convey, slow down, infiltrate and filter surface runoff water, reducing the pressure on traditional sewage systems. It consists of a complex layer structure composed of vegetation, growing medium soil, sand, geotextile, and gravel layers (from top to bottom). Additionally, it can include a water layer to simulate wet swales. The gravel layer can also overlay an underdrain system composed of PVC pipes to control the water flow. The geometry is managed by different constraints controlled by parameters, which are automatically updated in the next step to obtain the definitive intervention size. Both individual layer thickness and side slope were also configurable.

Fig. 2c shows an excerpt of the parameters needed to create the technique. Those marked with a red rectangle controlled the general size of the object: base, depth and width of the swale, thickness for growing medium layer, side slope, longitudinal slope, cross sectional area and final length. The three boolean parameters controlled the inclusion of check damns, fabric liner or underdrains. The last one set the pipe diameter in case underdrain check was enabled.

Furthermore, the object included additional alphanumeric parameters to store a variety of data (such as costs, link to the factsheet or location characteristics), which can serve for centralizing sustainability information, subsequent analyses or for interchange settings. Finally, a user-defined IFC class was established for exporting settings under IFC 4.3 (ISO 16739:2024). This value, still under study, was initially set to `ifcPavementType`, although other possible classes are being considered.

Fig. 2. Basic swale BIM object. (a) 3D view. (b) Section view with constraints (c) Property sets.

3.3 Automated creation of user-designed objects.

The creation of each object under specific design criteria was automated through the development of a Revit plugin that allowed users to work together with the design spreadsheet. By taking the corresponding starting family, the developed tool was able to automatically regenerate each technique according to the user's specifications. This plugin was built using the .NET API and coded with C# through Visual Studio, considering advantages as more efficient performance, ability to use Revit events, error handling or debugging possibilities.

Fig. 3 (right) shows the user interface for controlling object creation in Revit. The user is required to specify both the storage location of the design spreadsheet and the

folder in which the starting families are stored. In addition to selecting the appropriate results' sheet automatically, the user has the option of choosing any other sheet, provided the appropriate cell structure is maintained. Upon selecting the type of NbS on the available buttons, the plug-in acquires the design values, performs additional calculations to adjust parameters and geometry generation, and presents the desired technique in the correct dimensions and shape, as well as associate information in the property sets. The two tools (design spreadsheet and design authoring software) work concurrently so that the model is automatically updated as numerical changes are made. Once decided the definitive settings, object can be loaded into a project and located in the desired location.

Fig. 3. User interface for the Revit plug-in, and a dry-well after executing it.

4 Results

According to the catalog referenced in section 3.1, 13 different techniques were developed (Fig. 4), resulting in 22 different starting BIM objects due to several possible variations (e.g. inclusion of intermediate layers). Families were modeled under different categories, depending on the location (covering an area, as a retention pond or being a linear feature, as a filter strip), and standalone or hosted (as green roofs, that should have a roof as host). Geometry was created by means of CSG operations, with a special handicap when modelling objects with variable slope, as Revit does not allow to include side slope in built-in objects. In this case layer structure was modelled through nested loft operations restricted to one another, making it possible to parametrize a constant

gradient along the layers. Furthermore, each layer was characterized by its material with its physical parameters.

Finally, while some elements were created as whole objects, such as detention ponds or wetlands, others were presented as small sections, such as filter strips or swales, as their final shape depends on the path proposed by the user, that should match with the stored length parameter as well as the longitudinal slope.

Fig. 4. General view of the starting BIM objects for the NbS Library.

General sizing parameters were obtained from the design spreadsheet, but a variable amount of geometric additional parameters was necessary to correctly regenerate the geometry. Table 1 shows the number of parameters included in each object, distinguishing between those related to general sizing, those necessary for regenerating geometry according to the size (constraints), and those for controlling the existence of additional assets, as underdrains or inclusion of filter fabrics (boolean). A last column is added to the table to show the number of layers that made up each the technique.

Table 1. Parameters included in each technique.

NbS object	Size	Constraints	Boolean	Layers
01.Bioretention area	12	22	0	6
02.Detention basin	13	14	1	4
03.Filter strip	7	7	0	3
04.Green roof	11	7	0	6
05.Infiltration basin	11	21	2	4
06.Dry well	9	10	2	6
07.Infiltration trench	10	9	1	6
08.Permeable pavement	9	9	2	5
09.Retention pond	13	14	1	4

10. Filter drain	11	7	2	5
11. Grassed swale	8	3	1	5
12. Rain Garden	12	21	1	6
13. Wetland	23	17	1	4

In order to show the application and visualization of the NbS BIM objects, test scenarios were composed including NbS BIM objects as the example shown in Fig. 5, where permeable pavement is used in the parking located in the left corner of the figure. Furthermore, a grassed swale (between the road and the parking) and a detention pond were integrated. Information related to each technique is stored also in the model, as capacity, detention volume or infiltration rate, providing up-to-date design for fulfilling specific guidelines or performing subsequent analyses.

Fig. 5. Test scenario (Above, rendered model. Below, cross sections of the NbS).

5 Conclusions

The main objective of this communication is to show the developed NbS BIM library using Revit as a design authoring tool, inside a research focused on data-driven design of hybrid urban drainage systems. It was supported by a set of factsheets and a design spreadsheet for performing the necessary hydrological measurements that allowed to size each technique. The whole system was conceived as a reference guide for the selection and design of NbS and help decision makers in designing and defining storm

water management and urban runoff plans, including a predesign of mitigation strategies, and simplifying the creation of initial proposals. Revit was selected as the tool initial visualization, even though objects can be exported to IFC format in order to transfer them to any other platform. Aligned with Sustainable Development Goals 9 and 11, which delves into sustainable cities and innovation for infrastructures, BIM can support the effective incorporation of NbS to construction projects, enhancing the environmental studies in the design stage by including different indicator values as control capacity, socioeconomic criteria or even pollution. Future works would include to enlarge the existing library to additional drainage solutions, allow user-defined shapes, standardize semantics and resolve issues related with interchange to openBIM format.

Acknowledgements

This study is partially funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation program through the D4RUNOFF project and under grant agreement Number 101060638. Valerio Andrés-Valeri also like to thank the Spanish Ministry of Universities and the University of Cantabria for partially fund his research activities with EU Next Generation funds through the Maria Zambrano postdoctoral fellowship program.

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